

CYCLIC SOFTENING PHENOMENA IN FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Cyclic softening and cyclic hardening are well characterized fatigue responses of ductile isotropic metals. It has been clearly demonstrated that cyclic hardening never occurs in polymeric materials irrespective of structure. However, fiber reinforced polymers can show a variety of cyclic softening responses depending on the composite structure and the stress environment. Chopped fiber reinforced thermoplastics exhibit cyclic softening, the type and degree of softening being a function of the fiber volume and fiber type. Continuous graphite fiber reinforced polymers respond to cyclic stresses or strains in a manner which is a sensitive function of the relation between the applied stress and the fiber orientation. Along the fiber direction, the material is essentially cyclically stable. If the cyclic stress is applied at some angle to the fibers, the characteristic response is cyclic softening - the degree of softening is a direct function of the off-fiber angle. The strain accommodation mechanism(s) responsible for cyclic softening is discussed for the various composite structures. In addition, the implications of cyclic softening ("strength loss") in the long term applications of composites in dynamic structures is analyzed.

Introduction

In the design of structures subjected to dynamic loadings, the resistance to fatigue failure is frequently the critical mechanical property governing material selection. In the last decade, it has been clearly demonstrated in the application of metals to fatigue environments that the simple monotonic stress-strain relationship is not characteristic of the stress-strain relationship existing during fatigue. (1,2,3) Both cyclic softening and cyclic hardening can occur in metals in addition to cyclic stability - these phenomena are shown schematically in Figure No. 1.

Fig. 1. Schematic illustration of cyclic hardening and cyclic softening.

The importance of the characterization of changing stress-strain relationships under cyclic loading conditions is reflected in (a) the increasing design sophistication utilizing these data resulting in superior structural efficiency, and (b) the development of successful techniques for predicting the fatigue resistance of metals from rapid, simple tests.

In applying this fatigue methodology to polymeric materials, it has been well established that cyclic hardening never occurs. Single phase polymers can exhibit either cyclic stability or cyclic softening - the characteristics of the phenomena are much the same as observed in metals. In general, single phase polymers exhibiting ductility will show some degree of cyclic softening. (4,5) The present study investigates the effect of introducing fibers in the cyclic response of polymers, varying from low volume fractions of chopped fibers where the composite still exhibits ductility to the high volume fraction, continuous fiber (structural) composites which are essentially elastic to failure.

Materials

The materials used in the investigation fall into two classes. First, a ductile thermoplastic polymer (nylon 6/6) which is available with different volume fractions of chopped fibers (glass, graphite) - specifically nylon 6/6 with 0, 13, and 33 volume % chopped glass fibers,

and nylon 6/6 with 10, 20, 30 and 40 volume % chopped graphite fibers and nylon 6/6 with 20 glass/20 graphite. These materials exhibit a continuous transition in strength and ductility as a function of fiber volume. The second class of materials selected was continuous graphite fibers in epoxy. The specific material was 0°/90° (60 vol. %) woven graphite cloth in epoxy and is typical of the type of material used in structural applications - in particular, this material is elastic to failure.

Depending on the form of the material, cyclic testing was carried out in either: fully reversed or a tension-tension mode. Testing was carried out in strain control in a saw tooth wave form using an electro-hydraulic testing machine. A constant strain rate of 1% per second was normally utilized - higher strain rates were only utilized when it was established that no heating was incurred. These testing conditions were maintained to ensure all the observed effects were purely mechanical in nature and contained no thermal contribution.

Result and Discussion

(A) Chopped Fiber Composites

The glass fiber reinforced nylon composites exhibit the tensile properties shown in Figure 2. As the volume fraction of chopped glass

Fig. 2. Tensile stress-strain curves for nylon containing (a) 0% and (b) 13% and 33% of chopped glass fibers.

fibers increases, the modulus and strength increases and the ductility decreases. The introduction of the second phase (fibers) distributed uniformly throughout the nylon matrix also promotes deformation generally in the specimen and eliminates the localized cold drawing or yield drop phenomenon characteristic of ductile, single phase polymers.

Characteristic cyclic response data for nylon 6/6 are shown in Figure 3. The important points to note are (1) the immediate softening in tension and compression and (2) the attainment of a stable cyclically softened state which is maintained for most of the fatigue life (in Figure 3(a) the crack propagation stage is not shown). Obviously, the

Fig. 3. Typical cyclic response of nylon, as evidenced by (a) stress decrease, (b) hysteresis loops, and (c) cyclic stress-strain curves.

stress level characteristic of the stable cyclically softened state in relation to the imposed constant strain limits is more representative of the mechanical properties during fatigue than the monotonic stress-strain data. The cyclic softening as evidenced by change in hysteresis loops is shown in Figure 3(b). The degree of asymmetry of the loops is related to the particular deformation mechanisms operative during fatigue (4,5) and provide a continuous record of changing mechanisms. The total effect of cyclic softening can be summarized in the form of a cyclic stress-strain curve, Figure 3(c). It is clear that significant "weakening" of the material occurs during fatigue, and these data also confirm the validity of the use of cyclic stress-strain curves for designing polymers into dynamic structural applications.

The effect of introducing 13 volume % chopped glass fibers on the

Fig. 4. Typical cyclic response of nylon/13% glass as evidenced by (a) stress decrease, (b) hysteresis loops and (c) cyclic stress-strain curves.

cyclic response is shown in Figure 4. Immediate cyclic softening followed by a stable cyclically softened state indicates that the response is of exactly the same nature as the unreinforced matrix, c. f. Figure 3. The hysteresis loops tend to be more symmetric, characteristic of deformation mechanisms occurring uniformly throughout the specimen. However, phenomenologically the response is of the same type and only differs in degree. Consequently, a stable stress-strain curve can be defined, Figure 4(c), which can be considered as characteristic of the material during fatigue.

Increasing the volume fraction of chopped glass fibers to 33% produces cyclic changes not only in degree but also in kind. In Figure 5 it can be seen that immediate cyclic softening occurs in exactly the same manner as described above. However, instead of attaining a stable cyclically softened state, softening occurs continuously throughout the remainder of the fatigue life. Since a constant cyclically softened stress level is not attained, a new constant cyclic stress-strain relation cannot be defined. The usual practice in such situations is to define a pseudo cyclic stress-strain curve in which the stress at 50% of

Fig. 5. Typical cyclic response of nylon /33% glass.

the fatigue life is used as the stress point. It should be recognized that the cyclic stress-strain curve in such a material is not as definitive as the cyclic curves for materials which achieve a stable cyclic state.

The changes in softening characteristics as a function of volume fraction of glass fibers can be attributed to competing deformation mechanisms (4,5). The introduction of the fibers produces a capability of absorbing plastic deformation by fiber/matrix interfacial mechanisms. At low fiber volumes (13%), the interfacial mechanism is only a small fraction of the overall plastic deformation capability of the composite - the matrix still provides the primary mode of plastic accommodation and this dominates the overall response. Consequently, the low fiber volume composites behave in much the same way as the matrix homopolymer, namely a stable cyclically softened state. In contrast, increasing the volume fraction of fibers to 33% leads to the interfacial mechanism becoming a significant factor. However, examination of Figures 3, 4 and 5 indicates that the initial macroscopic softening is probably always dominated by bulk flow mechanisms, i.e., deformation occurring uniformly through the sample. This deduction is based on hysteresis loop changes and comparisons with other multiphase polymers (4,5). The interfacial mechanism comes into play during deformation in the softened state. The continuous softening in the high fiber volume composites is accompanied by a continuing change in hysteresis loop geometry. Such changes are evidence of competing strain accommodation mechanisms wherein one dominant mechanism is gradually replaced by an alternative mode. Thus, the gradual softening occurring in the 33% fiber material can be interpreted as a change from bulk deformation in the matrix to a state where a majority of the strain accommodation is achieved by matrix/fiber interfacial mechanisms.

The overall fatigue behavior can be summarized in the form of strain-life curves, Figure 6. The pattern of behavior is as expected on the basis of the strength/ductility combinations. In high strain, low cyclic fatigue materials capable of absorbing large amounts of plastic deformation show a superiority. If the data had been carried out to longer lives, the curves would cross and superior low strain fatigue resistance would be exhibited by the fiber reinforced materials since strength is the major requirement in this cyclic regime.

The utilization of chopped graphite fibers instead of glass fibers confirmed the generality of the above data. The cyclic response is essentially exactly similar. The pattern of behavior demonstrated by

Fig. 6. Fatigue life curves for nylon containing 0%, 13% and 33% chopped glass fibers.

Fig. 8. Schematic representation of materials with different stress-strain curves illustrating the different cyclic response to be expected from strain control (ϵ_1) and stress control (σ_1) fatigue tests.

Fig. 9. Initial nested hysteresis loops for nylon - 20% Gr - 20% Gl illustrating the cyclic softening phenomenon.

(B) Continuous Fiber Composites

Graphite fiber reinforced plastics in which the graphite fibers are continuous are high performance, structural materials with high fatigue resistance. Such materials differ from chopped fiber systems in that the properties are highly directional. These composites are elastic to failure along the fiber direction with no plastic strain accommodation mechanisms since all the mechanical properties are controlled by the fibers. Commonly, these composites are cross-plyed or woven into $0^\circ/90^\circ$ cloth to provide some degree of isotropy. Typically, a 60 volume % graphite fiber woven cloth in epoxy exhibits directional monotonic properties as shown in Figure 10. Along the fiber directions (0° and 90°), the composite has the highest strength and the lowest strain to failure. (The use of $0^\circ/90^\circ$ woven cloth in these tests as opposed to $0^\circ/90^\circ$ cross plied laminates is not significant - cross plied laminates exhibit exactly the same overall phenomena with only minor changes in degree.)

All the cyclic testing was performed in a tension-tension mode because of the geometry of the samples. Specimens tested along the fiber direction

Fig. 10. Variation in failure stress and strain with testing direction relative to fiber axes in woven graphite cloth.

Fig. 11. Hysteresis loops for graphite cloth - epoxy composite tested in fatigue with the stress parallel to the fiber direction ($\theta = 0$ or 90°) - initial loops and a loop at $N = 10,000$ are shown.

($\theta = 0^\circ, 90^\circ$) exhibited elastic behavior at all strain levels. Figure 11 shows typical hysteresis loops. The elastic nature of the strain accommodation is, of course, responsible for the high degree of fatigue resistance in the fiber direction. In contrast, Figure 12 shows typical hysteresis loops for $\theta = 15^\circ$ ($=75^\circ$) where obvious cyclic softening occurs. The amount of cyclic softening is increased when the stressing direction is deviated further from the fiber direction. Figure 13 illustrates the softening along direction $\theta = 30^\circ$ ($=60^\circ$).

Continuous fiber composites are designed on the basis that the stresses will always be borne by the fibers, and not by the fiber/matrix interface or the matrix. In complex stress environments, there will always be off-fiber stresses and the effects of these stresses is significant if major softening can occur. The mechanisms by which the

Fig. 12. Hysteresis loops for graphite cloth - epoxy composite tested in fatigue with stress direction at 75° to fiber axis ($\approx 15^\circ$).

Fig. 13(a). Hysteresis loops for graphite cloth - epoxy composite tested in fatigue with stress direction at 60° to fiber axis ($\approx 30^\circ$).

GRAPHITE CLOTH - EPOXY

Fig. 13. (b) Continuous strip chart recording showing stress decrease for fixed imposed strain limits for test in Fig. 13 (a).

cyclic softening occurs is of importance since it could affect the resistance along the fiber direction. For example, if the cyclic softening occurs by fiber/matrix interfacial degradation, the resulting interfacial weakening will directly affect the mechanical properties in all directions since the integrity of the composite is a direct function of interfacial cohesion. Graphite fibers are essentially elastic to failure and thus cannot exhibit cyclic softening. The epoxy matrix is semi-brittle and this class of materials is cyclically stable (4,5). Thus, the individual constituents of the composite would not promote cyclic softening. The cyclic softening due to off-fiber stresses in the composite must be due to either fiber/matrix interfacial deformation/degradation or induced plastic deformation capability of the matrix due to the constraining influence of the fibers. The interfacial degradation mechanism appears to be most probable of the two potential mechanisms because gradual softening occurs throughout the fatigue life.

The effect of off-fiber stresses on the fatigue resistance of continuous fiber reinforced composites can be judged from Figure 14.

Fig. 14. Relative fatigue resistance of graphite cloth - epoxy composite as a function of the angle θ between the fiber orientation and the stress axis - data is normalized relative to ultimate tensile strength.

All the data has been normalized to unity at $2N_f=1$ (i.e. the tensile strength). The long life fatigue resistance (e.g. $2N_f=10^7$) at $\theta=0^\circ$ is extremely high, approximately 0.75 of the tensile strength. By contrast, at $\theta=45^\circ$ the fatigue life is only about 0.25 of the tensile strength. In absolute terms, the long life fatigue stress at $\theta=45^\circ$ is only about 1/8 of the fatigue stress at $\theta=0^\circ$. Consequently, even minor stresses can be significant in composite applications subjected to dynamic environments.

Conclusions

Cyclic softening must be allowed for in the use of all fiber reinforced structural polymers. In chopped fiber systems, the pseudo-isotropic nature of the material facilitates characterization of this phenomenon and imposes no severe dilemma in design. Continuous fiber reinforced composites require more comprehensive characterization because of the high degree of anisotropy of these materials. Small cyclic stresses in off-fiber directions can have effects on the overall integrity of the composite, and these must be allowed for in structural applications.

References

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